

**METACOGNITION AWARENESS IN SPORTS AND NON-SPORTS PROSPECTIVE
TEACHERS**

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ABSTRACT

We usually have an idea about what we are doing while we are doing it, but it is difficult to enhance a process if we don't know what we are doing in present. The present study was conducted to explore the relationship between Metacognitive awareness in sports and non-sports prospective teachers. Metacognition is an individual's ability to be aware of his or her thought processes. When applied effectively, metacognition improves strategic thinking to help individual reason through a given task. The study reveals that there is no significant difference found in metacognitive awareness between the sports and non-sports prospective teachers.

Key Words: Metacognition, Sports and Non-sports

INTRODUCTION

For a variety of reasons, metacognition has become one of the most popular topics among academicians. One of the reasons for this is because metacognition is one of the most essential aspects influencing people's problem-solving habits. Also, metacognition is a critical structure that influences an individual's learning process. Learners' cognitions or their knowledge about cognition as a whole refers to how much they pick up with their own memories and acquiring methods. Monitoring of cognition refers to a set of metacognitive activities through which an individual has ability to control his or her learning and thinking, and connects the two together. In other words, it refers to strategies or skills that promote comprehension and enable the achievement of a goal.

Individuals must now plan and schedule their studies, as well as have a working knowledge of their own cognitive processes, in order to be effective while juggling their busy study schedules. As a result, all of these are aspects of metacognitive awareness. Furthermore, an individual's metacognitive awareness is seen as a vital aspect in boosting their achievement, learning throughout their lives, creative and critical thinking, and self-confidence. As a result, it's crucial to figure out what level of metacognitive awareness prospective teachers have and

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See, if it varies depending on factors like gender or class level. Different educators have used the term Metacognition.

Kuiper (2002), states that learners with a certain level of self-regulation and strategy of metacognition get a better academic achievement. He also emphasizes the benefits of metacognition, which he claims can only be acquired once, including how it fosters accountability, reflective thinking, and speedy decision-making. Flavell in 1976 suggested the concept of 'metacognition'. Flavell states metacognition as knowledge and cognitive regarding cognitive processes, also, knowledge of Individual's own cognitive process and utilizing this knowledge to regulate cognitive processes, the knowledge of which strategies be employed with which goals, and the assessment of individual process before and after performance.

METACOGNITION IN EDUCATION

In education, metacognition is usually examined in the context of self-regulated learning, skill seen in high achieving students. In learning process application, self- monitoring entails developing a plan to achieve a task-specific goal, monitoring and controlling one's going performance, and self-reflection.

It is the awareness of the acquisition of mental organization skills and the ability to consciously and deliberately monitor and one's own thought processes. Metacognition is widely acknowledged as a critical talent for 21st Century learning and the main driver of student's self regulated learning behaviors. Metacognition was more of a curiosity in the beginning, and several psychologists questioned if it was even a workable concept, Today, I believe the question is how it might be best understood, evaluated, and improved, not if it is a valid concept. The concept of metacognition includes two components – (a) knowledge of cognition and (b) regulation of cognition. Knowledge of cognition deals with all the concepts, that are affiliated to our thinking processes like own concept of knowledge, self intelligence, attention, study habits etc.; the mechanisms through which our thought processes are controlled, say, orientation, planning, monitoring, testing, repairing, evaluating, and reflecting, are all included in the monitoring of cognitive processes (Manual for Meta-Cognition Inventory,2003). Concerning metacognitive development, simply providing learners with highly regimented and structured instruction in metacognitive knowledge without metacognitive experience or quite reverse seems to be insufficient for and does not guarantee the development of metacognitive control and self-regulation (Livingston, 1996 & 1997). Thereby, in fostering a culture of metacognition in learners and classroom settings, the most efficacious approach, though there

are several approaches, is the one into which both components of metacognition, namely metacognitive knowledge, and metacognitive regulation are incorporated.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Karaoglu and Turan (2020) study proved that physical education teacher's metacognitive awareness was low along with low negative relationship between the metacognitive awareness and the avoid of performance tendency under success orientation.

Baspinar and Ziyagil (2019) study revealed that there was no significant difference in the favor of athlete participants in all sub-dimensions in male and female groups. Females in sedentary group and male in athlete group had significantly higher MAS values.

RATIONALE

We usually have an idea about what we are doing while we are doing it, but it is difficult to enhance a process if we don't know what we are doing in present. If one of the goals of education is to prepare students to be lifelong learners, it is critical to assist students in being aware of themselves as learners and taking charge of their own actions.

The study has emerged out of the experiences of the investigator during teaching practice of B.Ed. Teachers nowadays, are unaware of the word "metacognition," and as an outcome, they fail to innovate metacognitive pattern into the classroom. As maximum students unknowingly catch metacognitive knowledge and skills from their parents, peers, and especially their teachers to some level. Therefore, teachers play a crucial and vital part of any society's labor. Teachers are considered to represent society's socio-cultural perspectives; it is said that no one can climb above the level of a teacher. Their composition, psychological tendencies, sociocultural features, and cognitive processes must all be thoroughly understood before we can confidently produce the next generation of teachers. As teachers who are involved in physical activities has an increase in their socialization and quality of life. It is important to recognize how prospective teachers with sports perform in learning environment, their focus on metacognitive abilities, their pedagogical skills at the time of commencing their professional life in future than the non-sports prospective teachers. The study's finding will help teachers and authorities in terms of convincing them of the importance of training prospective teachers about metacognition and its impact on thinking in order to gain a better awareness of their surroundings.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

To study and compare the metacognitive awareness among sports and non- sports prospective teachers.

HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

There is no significant difference in the metacognitive awareness of sports and non-sports prospective teachers.

DELIMITATION OF THE STUDY

- The present study will be delimited to Government College of Education, Chandigarh only.
- The present study will be confined to sports and non-sports prospective teachers only.

METHODOLOGY

The present study entails the normative survey method of research.

SAMPLE

The purposive random sampling method was followed for the present study. The data was collected from 50 prospective teachers out of which 25 were sports affiliated and remaining 25 as general. The area of data collection was confined to Government College of Education, Chandigarh.

TOOLS

Meta Cognition Inventory (MCI) by Dr.Govil (2003)

PROCEDURE

The tool was administered to the two groups after making the subjects aware of the objective of the investigation. The scoring of the test was done technically thereafter. The collected data was analyzed by using the basic and elementary statistical computations such as mean, median etc. for the scores so obtained. Tables were formed to highlight the results.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

The analysis and interpretation of the data was done by calculating the Mean, SD, t-value etc. as per the requirement of the objectives of the study.

		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	Sports	92.4800	25	10.89388	2.17878
	Non-sports	90.3600	25	11.32431	2.26486

Table 1 shows the descriptive statistics. We see, Sports prospective teachers mean scores are higher.

Now, beneath 'Paired differences' we see the descriptive statistics for the difference between the two.

		Paired Differences					t	df	Sig.(2-tailed)
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
					Lower	Upper			
Pair 1	Sports – Non-sports	2.12000	14.63819	2.92764	-3.92235	8.16235	.724	24	.476

Table 2 shows, The T-value = 0.724

We have 24 degree of freedom

Our significance is 0.476 at 0.05 level

Here, we can see the significance value is greater than 0.05, which indicates that there is no significant difference in Metacognitive awareness between sports and non-sports prospective teachers significant at 0.05 level.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

In our daily life, providing knowledge and skills have become one of the aims of the education. High success motivated people who study, take up challenges, undertake effort and try to sort out the difficulties when face, whereas, low motivated people will set goals which are easy to accomplish, makes an excuse for their failures and so on. Meta-cognition helps people to know what they know and how they can use their knowledge to a better end. As teachers who are

involved in physical activities has an increase in their socialization and quality of life. It is important to recognize how prospective teachers with sports perform in learning environment, their focus on metacognitive abilities, their pedagogical skills at the time of commencing their professional life in future than the non-sports prospective teachers. The present study was mainly dealt with the metacognitive awareness between sports and non-sports prospective teachers. After analyzing and interpreting the data, it was found that there is no significant difference in awareness between the sports and non-sports prospective teachers. Yet, Sports prospective teachers mean scores were higher than the non-sports.

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